

FORECASTING THE LOAD ON THE ELECTRIC GRID OF A MINING AND PROCESSING PLANT**Kupin A.**

*Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of Computer Systems and Networks,
Kryvyi Rih National University, Ukraine, Kryvyi Rih.
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7569-1721>*

Lyashenko V.

*candidate technical Sciences, State enterprise "Ukrainian Research and Design and Intelligence Institute of
Industrial Technology", Ukraine, Zhovti Vody
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8361-4179>*

Holiver V.

*PhD, Post doc., Kryvyi Rih National University, Kryvyi Rih, Ukraine.
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8276-5992>*

Sherstnev Y.

*PhD student at the Department of Electrical Engineering,
Kryvyi Rih National University, Kryvyi Rih, Ukraine
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3210-5552>*

ABSTRACT

The relevance of the work is due to the need for a comprehensive study of the power supply system of the efficiency of managing the consumption of electrical energy based on predicting the load on the power grid of concentrating plants. The accuracy of its forecast will significantly simplify the process of making managerial decisions in strategic and operational planning and minimize the cost of electricity for the production of a unit of output (ore concentrate).

Purpose: substantiation of the efficiency of electricity consumption in the enrichment and processing of ores based on the management and forecasting of the load on the electrical network of concentrating plants. This will make it possible to use industrial energy storage devices at the right time to reduce the consumption from the network during peak hours (when using a two-rate tariff) or in the peak zone of the day (when using a differentiated tariff for electrical energy).

Objects: enrichment plants, which are characterized by the complexity of determining the energy characteristics of process equipment and effective management of electricity consumption based on predicting the load on the power grid.

Methods: methods of complex generalization, analysis and evaluation of practical experience and scientific achievements in the field of managerial decision-making in strategic and operational planning and minimization of electricity costs for the production of a unit of output were used. In particular, the analysis of literary sources was carried out; used the method of theoretical generalizations with the use of mathematical statistics, physical and mathematical modeling; calculations and feasibility studies, laboratory and full-scale experimental studies, as well as industrial tests in the conditions of operating enterprises according to standard and new methods with the participation of the authors.

Results. On the basis of experimental studies, the factors influencing the consumption of electrical energy and to be included in the developed machine learning model were determined, which will significantly simplify the process of making managerial decisions in the strategic and operational planning of electrical energy costs and minimize the cost of electricity for the production of a unit of output. It has been established that the important features are the ambient temperature, the correlation coefficient of which with the target variable - the total uncontrolled load - is 0.17, humidity (correlation coefficient was -0.22), weekend/working day sign (correlation coefficient -0.33), day of the week (correlation coefficient -0.38), time data (correlation coefficient for time 0.19, for month and year < 0.068). A machine learning model based on the extreme gradient boosting regression model (XGB Regressor) is proposed, which makes it possible to obtain the most reliable forecast of the load on the concentrator's power grid. The average absolute prediction error of these models was 3.51, and the coefficient of determination was 0.84 and 0.87 for the training and test samples, respectively. The results of the study can be adapted for other objects. It was noted that the modeling of the work of fuzzy intelligent control system (ISC) showed potential opportunities for reducing the total energy consumption by 15-35% in the modes of additional hydroaccumulating EE generation (two-rate tariff was studied) in the conditions of various enterprises involved in the extraction and beneficiation of iron ore raw materials.

Keywords: washing plant, energy saving, forecasting, modeling, regression, correlation, machine learning, power grid load, management efficiency.

1. Introduction

1.1. Statement of the problem. Numerous studies in developed countries are devoted to energy saving issues [1, 2]. Scientists study energy saving issues in various aspects, including economic, environmental,

technological, etc. [3, 4]. The use of modern information technologies, in particular data mining technologies, has significantly expanded the capabilities of researchers in various fields, including solving problems related to energy saving [5, 6]. Therefore, the study and substantiation of the efficiency of managing electricity

consumption based on forecasting the load on the power grid of mining and processing plants is an important scientific, practical and social task that requires prompt solution [7, 8].

2. The object of research and its technological audit

The object of the study is the management of electricity consumption based on forecasting the load on the power grid of a mining and processing plant. One of the most problematic areas is the complexity of forecasting electricity consumption of energy-intensive mining and metallurgical production. The accuracy of its forecast allows to significantly simplify the process of making management decisions in strategic and operational planning of electricity costs and minimize electricity costs for the production of a unit of finished goods [9, 10].

3. Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the efficiency of managing electricity consumption based on forecasting the load on the power grid of a mining and processing plant. This will significantly simplify the process of making management decisions in strategic and operational planning of electricity costs and minimize electricity costs for the production of a unit of finished goods, in particular, mining raw materials.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved:

1. Determine the factors affecting electricity consumption and subject to inclusion in the developed machine learning model.
2. Assess the closeness of the relationship between the features and the target variable of the model, confirming or rejecting the need to include certain factors in the model.
3. Develop a machine learning model that allows the most accurate forecasting of electricity consumption based on data from previous periods of electricity consumption and selected factors.

4. Research existing solutions to the problem

The work by scientists from the University of Dayton (USA) presents data mining that uses known building and energy characteristics to predict the energy consumption of homes, which in aggregate can be considered representative of all residential buildings within the entire community. The approach described in [11] estimates the consumption and savings of natural gas, as well as the corresponding implementation costs associated with taking the most effective measures to reduce energy consumption. The study uses an artificial neural network (ANN) model that estimates natural gas savings and the standardized costs of energy saving measures in buildings. Researchers from the Tokyo University of Science have developed a method for optimizing the energy consumption of buildings (using a hotel as an example). The essence of the method is a combination of metaheuristics and machine learning: metaheuristics are used to determine the optimal operating schedules for each device, and the deep neural network machine learning technique is used to predict the optimal operation of integrated cooling tower systems (a cooling tower is an industrial unit designed to cool circulating water used to remove heat

from process equipment in circulating water supply systems). The regression models used in this study were linear multiple regression analysis, random forest, and deep neural network (DNN). The method proposed in [12] can reduce daily operating costs by more than 13.4%.

The work of Chinese scientists is devoted to forecasting electricity consumption. They developed a new forecasting framework based on machine learning with a three-level ensemble decomposition approach. Using the model proposed in the researchers obtained the results of forecasting China's electricity consumption for the period 2020 - 2024. In the work of other Chinese researchers, the problem of electricity losses during the operation of shopping centers was considered. Scientists proposed a model for diagnosing energy saving in a shopping center building based on an improved PSO-SVM neural network [13].

In [14], the use of a clustering algorithm to obtain an initial dataset with energy-saving characteristics from historical data on electricity consumption is described. Then, using the Adaboost algorithm, the PSO-SVM neural network was optimized and the criteria for assessing abnormal energy consumption were established. Thanks to the resulting model, the energy saving diagnostic level was increased from -1.1% to 11.9%, and the problematic moments arising during the operation of the air conditioning system in shopping centers were successfully diagnosed.

The study by German scientists is devoted to the analysis of plant energy load curves based on machine learning, since an accurate understanding of energy load curves is the key to effective management of plant energy systems and the basis for several energy applications (e.g. forecasts, anomaly detection). The paper describes a methodology combining unsupervised 1D clustering and methods based on multivariate forecasting. The methods presented in [15] were tested on actual plant data. The researchers developed two methods for analyzing energy load curves: a 1D clustering algorithm and a multivariate approach based on ANN forecasts, taking into account the necessary influencing factors with the real state of the plants and external weather conditions. Both methods were compared regarding the best fit to the real values based on the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) results. Although the multivariate approach provides higher accuracy results, the difference in MAPE between the methods is small. Thus, 1D clustering already provides good results with limited effort. The researchers note that, although the demonstration of the methodology focuses on the analysis of electrical load curves, the presented approach can be transferred to other forms of energy (e.g., compressed air, process gas, etc.) [16, 17].

Thus, the results of the analysis allow us to conclude that electricity is one of the most important resources for industrial production and in the service sector. Having an accurate forecast of electricity consumption allows us to significantly simplify the process of making management decisions in strategic and operational planning of electricity costs, and, consequently, to minimize the electricity costs spent on the production of a unit of output. In addition, with a reliable forecast,

it becomes possible to modernize the energy consumption management process. The use of an electrical energy storage system allows us to accumulate electricity at a minimum tariff plan so that during peak loads there is enough electricity for the uninterrupted operation of the facility [18, 19].

5. Research methods

To achieve the goal set in the work:

- an analysis of literary sources was performed;
- a method of theoretical generalizations was used using mathematical statistics, physical and mathematical modeling;
- calculations and technical and economic justifications, laboratory and full-scale experimental studies, as well as industrial tests in the conditions of operating enterprises were carried out using standard and new methods with the participation of the authors, which are more fully presented in the works [20, 21].

6. Research results

Many enterprises and organizations have installed energy management systems (EMS Systems), which allow to reduce the payment for electric energy due to the rational use of the power supply system. For example, in the works of the authors [22, 23], the problem of creating an intelligent system of predictive energy consumption management in the conditions of extraction and processing of iron ore raw materials in the mines of the enterprises of Krivbass, Ukraine, was set and successfully solved based on the use of fuzzy logic. At the same time, the intelligent control system (ICS) demonstrated the following results:

1. The use of a two-rate tariff "Day / Night" without the use of fuzzy ICS leads to an increase in daily costs for consumed electricity (EE) by 12.9% with single-channel regulation of water drainage and, accordingly, by 7.1% with two-channel control of ore flow and water drainage simultaneously. However, the use of fuzzy controllers allows to compensate for these losses.

2. The use of the ISC with fuzzy 3-channel regulation of ore flow, water drainage and ventilation allows, under the conditions of a two-part tariff (due to more rational redistribution over daily intervals), to reduce the costs of consumed EE (for example, according to the Rodina mine, with an increase in daily EE consumption by 4.5%, total costs are reduced by 2.5%).

3. Modeling the operation of fuzzy ISCs showed potential for reducing total energy consumption by 15-35% in the modes of additional pumped-storage generation of EE (a two-part tariff was studied) in the conditions of various enterprises with underground iron ore mining.

All of the above indicates a significant potential for the use of such intelligent approaches and predictive EMS systems. A high-quality forecast of the electrical load is required to form optimal control actions on the electrical energy storage system. Thus, a sufficiently accurate forecast of electrical energy consumption allows the use of electrical energy storage devices and the most optimal management of electrical energy resources. The study was implemented using the example of forecasting the electrical load on an office building. However, the results of the study can also be adapted to

an industrial facility with an energy management system. The data for the study were taken from open sources of the ANO "University of the National Technological Initiative 2035" [24].

6.1. Description of materials and research methods

As part of the study, a machine learning model was created in the Python programming language version 3.10.0 in the Jupyter Notebook environment, which ensures a fairly high accuracy of forecasting the electricity load of an office building. The choice of the programming language is justified by the presence of many libraries containing various regression models, including models whose algorithms are based on neural networks. Python is widely used in machine learning, including for supervised learning and forecasting tasks, since it combines the simplicity of syntax and high performance in data processing. The following libraries were used: Numpy and Pandas (for calculations and data manipulation), Matplotlib and Seaborn (for data visualization), Scikit-learn (for data preprocessing and loading regression model instances) and XGBoost (for importing an extreme gradient boosting model instance). Jupyter Notebook was chosen as the implementation environment as a convenient development tool for machine learning tasks. In Jupyter Notebook, it is possible to split the code into separate fragments, execute them in any order, and track the result immediately after running each fragment. In addition, Jupyter Notebook allows you to store code, graphs, formulas, images, comments in one document and supports the ability to import and export documents of other formats (e.g., html, github) [25, 26].

6.2. Intelligent data processing

The initial data sample (data set) is the readings of the ICP DAS sensors installed in the office building under consideration. It has four electrical energy inputs, each with a meter. The receivers of electrical energy are office equipment (computers, printers, projector, screens, interactive whiteboard, etc.), air conditioners, lighting, household appliances for the dining room, elevator, etc. Electricity is also consumed for roof heating and is a controlled load, so it is not considered in the study. The hourly load for each electrical energy input (excluding the storage device) in kW and the reliability indicator of power measurements by the building inputs are known. The model was built in several stages.

The first stage was exploratory data analysis and preprocessing. This stage included: analysis of the initial data set, processing of missing values, data visualization using graphs reflecting the consumption of electrical energy over time with a positive reliability indicator of power measurements by four electrical energy inputs to the building (Figure 1-4).

In general, the graphs show that the distribution of values is maintained within boundaries close to the average, but there are outliers, some of which can be explained. Thus, in April-May 2020, there was a significant decrease in consumption for all building entrances, which was caused by the Covid-19 pandemic and the transition of most employees to remote work. At the next stage, the features and the target variable

were defined. The target variable is the total uncontrolled load (y) for all building entrances. The following factors were considered: weather (temperature t , humidity U , wind speed Ff , horizontal visibility VV , dew point temperature Td) and time data (month, day, hour,

day of the week). In addition, another feature used in the study was the weekend or working day factor (holy). For this, the production calendar for the period under consideration was loaded and integrated with the data set under study.

Fig.1. Electricity consumption schedule of the first input (Bus1): X – Date, years and months; Y – Volume, $kW*hour$

Fig.2. Electricity consumption schedule of the second input (Bus2): X – Date, years and months; Y – Volume, $kW*hour$

Fig.3. Electricity consumption schedule of the third input (Bus3)

Fig.4. Electricity consumption schedule of the forth input (Bus4): X – Date, years and months; Y – Volume, kW*hour

6.3. Theory of the issue

The authors compiled a correlation matrix calculated using the formula for the paired correlation coefficient (1), where x and y are the pairwise selected factors and the target variable (Figure 5), according to the expression:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{xy - x \cdot y}{\sigma(x) \cdot \sigma(y)} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 5. Correlation matrix: X - Correlation factors; Y - Target variable

As a result of the analysis of the obtained correlation matrix, the factors wind speed Ff , horizontal visibility range VV , dew point temperature Td were removed from the data set, since their influence on the target variable was the least. It is worth noting that the features are rather weakly related to each other, therefore, it can be concluded that there is no intercorrelation. The original data set was divided into training and test samples. The next step was to select a machine learning model and build a forecast. The models used in the study were: linear regression (LinearRegression, Lasso, Ridge), k-nearest neighbors (KNeighborsRegressor), decision tree (DecisionTreeRegressor), random forest (RandomForestRegressor), stochastic gradient descent (SGDRegressor), support vector linear regression (LinearSVR), multilayer perceptron (MLPRegressor), and extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost). The quality metrics values for each of the models used are given in Table.

Comparison of model quality metrics

Quality metrics Model	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Explained Variance Score (EVS)	Mean Square Error (MSE)	Mean squared logarithmic error (MSLE)	Maximum Error (ME)	Median Absolute Error (MedAE)	Coefficient of determination (R ²)
Linear Regression	6.03	-0.68	50.14	0.11	17.63	5.77	-0.72
Lasso	5.97	-0.73	49.72	0.11	17.86	5.63	-0.77
Ridge	6.04	-0.68	50.14	0.11	17.63	5.77	-0.72
KNeighbors Regressor	5.13	0.59	47.24	0.11	28.93	3.84	0.58
DecisionTree Regressor	4.14	0.84	25.18	0.06	24.14	3.54	0.84
Random Forest Regressor	3.9	0.86	20.17	0.05	14.17	3.45	0.86
SGDRegressor	9.51	-0.55	128.7	0.25	29.73	8.64	-12.17
Linear SVR	5.48	-3.57	54.57	0.09	21.12	4.21	-3.03
MLPRegressor	3.89	0.85	20.49	0.08	14.43	3.54	0.857
XGBRegressor	3.51	0.89	15.24	0.07	12.36	3.73	0.87

Forecasting was carried out separately for each input to the building, the forecast results were summed up into the final indicator of the electrical load on the building. The following metrics were used to assess the quality of machine learning models:

1). Mean absolute forecast error (MAE). This function calculates the mean absolute error of the corresponding expected value of the absolute loss or error. If is the predicted value of the i -th sample value (samples) and y_i is the corresponding true value, then the MAE over samples is determined according to the expression:

$$\text{MAE}(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{n_{\text{samples}}} \sum_{i=0}^{n_{\text{samples}}-1} |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (2)$$

2). Explained variance score explained_variance_score (EVS). If is the estimated target result, y is the corresponding (correct) target output and Var is the variance (squared standard deviation), then the explained variance is calculated according to the expression:

$$\text{explained_variance}(y, \hat{y}) = 1 - \frac{\text{Var}\{y - \hat{y}\}}{\text{Var}\{y\}} \quad (3)$$

The best possible estimate for this indicator is 1, a lower value means worse performance of the forecasting model.

3). Maximum error max_error (ME) calculates the maximum residual error – the largest difference between the predicted and true values. If is the predicted value of the i -th sample value and y_i is the corresponding true value, then the maximum error is determined according to the expression:

$$\text{Max Error}(y, \hat{y}) = \max(|y_i - \hat{y}_i|) \quad (4)$$

4). The mean square error mean_squared_error (MSE) calculates the average square difference between the predicted and actual values. Accordingly, $\text{MSE} > 0$ always serves as a measure of the quality of

the estimate - the closer the MSE values are to zero, the more accurate the model. Calculated according to the expression:

$$\text{MSE}(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{n_{\text{samples}}} \sum_{i=0}^{n_{\text{samples}}-1} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (5)$$

5). Mean squared logarithmic error of regression mean_squared_log_error (MSLE). Loss (L) is the average value of the observed data of the squared differences between the log-transformed true and predicted values, or written as a formula:

$$L(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N (\log(y_i + 1) - \log(\hat{y}_i + 1))^2 \quad (6)$$

This loss can be interpreted as a measure of the ratio between the true and predicted values according to the expression:

$$\log(y_i + 1) - \log(\hat{y}_i + 1) = \log \frac{y_i + 1}{\hat{y}_i + 1} \quad (7)$$

6). Median absolute error (MedAE). This metric is particularly interesting because it is robust to outliers. The loss is calculated by taking the median of the absolute differences between the target and the prediction. If is the predicted value of the i -th sample value and y_i is the corresponding true value, then the MedAE estimated from n samples is determined according to the expression:

$$\text{MedAE}(y, \hat{y}) = \text{median}(|y_1 - \hat{y}_1|, \dots, |y_n - \hat{y}_n|) \quad (8)$$

The best MedAE value is 0.0.

7). The coefficient of determination r^2 _score (R^2) is the proportion of variance explained by the independent variables in the model. It is used as a universal measure of the dependence of one random variable on many others. The best value is 1.0. If is the predicted value of the i -th sample value and y_i is the corresponding true value for the total n samples, R^2 is calculated according to the expression:

$$R^2(y, \hat{y}) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (9)$$

6.4. Evaluation of research results

Наилучшие показатели качества прогноза показали модели:

1). XGBoost (r^2_score для обучающей выборки 0.84, r^2_score для тестовой выборки 0.87, MAE 3.51);

2). MLPRegressor (r^2_score для обучающей выборки 0.948, r^2_score для тестовой выборки 0.857, MAE 3.89);

3). RandomForestRegressor (r^2_score для обучающей выборки 0.984, r^2_score для тестовой выборки 0.864, MAE 3.90);

4). DecisionTreeRegressor (r^2_score для обучающей выборки 1.0, r^2_score для тестовой выборки 0.841, MAE 4.09).

The parameters for these models were selected using cross-validation, a method for evaluating machine learning models by training several of them on subsets of the available input data and evaluating them on another additional subset. Cross-validation was performed using the GridSearchCV tool, which creates models based on the given parameters and selects the most relevant one. The actual values of the target variable and the predicted indicators for the XGBRegressor model are shown in the graphs (Figure 6-9).

Fig. 6. Schedule of forecast and actual values of electric energy consumption for the first entry into the building: X – Date, years and months; Y – Volume, kW*hour

Fig. 7. Schedule of forecast and actual values of electric energy consumption for the second entry into the building: X – Date, years and months; Y – Volume, kW*hour

Fig. 8. Schedule of forecast and actual values of electric energy consumption for the third entry into the building: X – Date, years and months; Y – Volume, kW*hour

Fig. 9. Schedule of forecast and actual values of electric energy consumption for the fourth entry into the building: X – Date, years and months; Y – Volum

The XGBRegressor model is a special case of gradient boosting and belongs to the class of ensemble methods, which by definition combine predictions from several models. Gradient boosting is a method whose algorithm includes loops for iteratively adding models to the ensemble. It begins with initializing the ensemble using a single model, the prediction results of which may be quite inaccurate, but subsequent additions to the ensemble eliminate these errors. Extreme gradient boosting is an improved implementation of gradient boosting that is superior in prediction accuracy with less execution time [27].

6.5. Implementation of research results

As a result of the conducted research, the initial data were analyzed, pre-processed, and machine learning models were built, among which the most accurate was the extreme gradient boosting model. It is worth noting that the accuracy of this machine learning model on the test sample is higher than on the training sample, which indicates the adequacy of the model to the experimental data and, as a result, the reliability of the obtained forecast of the load on the power grid [28].

It is shown that the replacement of the two-rate (“Nich/Pik”) tariff without the stagnation of fuzzy ISC leads to an increase in additional costs per household by 12.9% with a single-channel regulated water supply and by 7.1% with a double-channel keruvanny with ore flow and water flow at the same time. However, the use of fuzzy controls makes it possible to compensate for costs.

6.6. Effectiveness of research results

With the help of the proposed model, operational and strategic planning of resource expenditures for electric power needs is possible, which, in turn, allows improving the process of making management decisions. It was noted that the modeling of the work of fuzzy ISC showed potential opportunities for reducing the total energy consumption by 15-35% in the modes of additional hydroaccumulating EE generation (two-rate tariff was studied) in the conditions of various enterprises involved in the extraction and beneficiation of iron ore raw materials.

6.7. Promising research directions

Promising areas of research are, firstly, in-depth factor analysis, the search for new features and their study for the possibility of inclusion in the model for forecasting the consumption of electrical energy. Secondly, the improvement of machine learning methods in terms of interpreting the results obtained with their help [29, 30].

7. SWOT analysis of research results

Strengths. A machine learning model has been created that can be used to obtain a fairly accurate hourly forecast of electricity consumption based on data from previous periods using a minimum of external data (weather, production calendar, time data).

Weaknesses. In the process of managing electricity consumption, extraordinary events are possible (for example, equipment failures, power outages, Covid-19 pandemics and, as a result, the transition of some employees to remote work), the impact of which on consumption and electricity is significant, but the developed model does not take these factors into account.

Accordingly, if such events are long-term, the model will not show accurate results.

Opportunities. Taking into account a larger number of factors affecting the process of electricity consumption, the accuracy of the model will increase. Based on this, it is advisable to comprehensively consider the object of electricity consumption: existing electricity receivers, the technological process and conduct a factor analysis.

Threats. The model is designed to be embedded in the management decision support system used at the operational and strategic resource planning level. Therefore, the decision maker draws up an electricity consumption plan based on his own professional experience and intuition, but taking into account the data provided by the model.

8. Conclusion

Based on the conducted research and the obtained results of substantiation of the efficiency of electricity consumption management, as well as forecasting the load on the power grid, the authors made the following conclusions.

1. The factors influencing electricity consumption and subject to inclusion in the developed machine learning model were determined, which will significantly simplify the process of making management decisions in strategic and operational planning of electricity costs and minimize electricity costs per unit of production.

2. It was established that important features are ambient temperature, the correlation coefficient of which with the target variable - the total uncontrolled load - is 0.17, humidity (the correlation coefficient was -0.22), the weekend/working day indicator (the correlation coefficient is -0.33), day of the week (the correlation coefficient is -0.38), time data (the correlation coefficient for time is 0.19, for month and year < 0.068).

3. A machine learning model based on the gradient boosting algorithm was developed, which allows for accurate prediction of electricity consumption using supervised learning technology. The average absolute prediction error of this model was 3.51, and the determination coefficient was 0.84 and 0.87 for the training and test samples, respectively.

Acknowledgements

The authors express their gratitude for valuable and constructive comments and recommendations to specialists of the departments of "Automated Electromechanical Systems in Industry and Transport", "Computer Systems and Networks" (Krivoy Rog National University, Krivoy Rog, Ukraine), State Enterprise "Ukrainian Research and Design Institute of Industrial Technology", Zhovti Vody, Ukraine and others, special thanks to the reviewers of the article.

References

1. Gale Boyd, E. Mark Curtis, Su Zhang. Impact of Strategic Energy Management Practices on Energy Efficiency: Evidence from Plant-Level Data. – Summer Study on Energy Efficiency in Industry 2021.

2. Palamarchuk A.G. Analysis of the current state of energy saving in the Russian industry. – Moscow: Scientific Papers of the Free Economic Society of Russia, 2020. – pp. 270-282.

3. Popadko N.V., Naydenova V.M. Energy saving and efficiency improvement as a vector of development of the global energy complex. – Moscow: Innovation and investment, 2020. – No 5. – pp. 91-95.

4. Islamova V.M., Mustafin T.R., Kantemirov I.F. An integrated approach to the use of secondary energy resources at a compressor station. – Transportation and storage of petroleum products and hydrocarbon raw materials, 2020. – No 2. – pp. 27-31.

5. Zhavoronkova N.G., Shpakovskii Yu.G. Energy strategy-2035: legal problems of innovation development and environmental safety. – O. E. Kutafin's university press, 2020. – pp. 31-47.

6. O. Sinchuk, A. Kupin, I. Sinchuk, I. Kozakevych, I. Peresunko. Simulating of fuzzy controlling of power streams in conditions of underground extraction of iron ore // Proceedings of the International Scientific and Technical Conference "Problems of Modern Electrical Engineering - 2020 (PSE -2020)". June 8 - 12, 2020. Kyiv, Ukraine. NTUU "KPI named after I. Sikorsky".

7. Usmanova T. Kh., Isakov D. A. Important aspects of power costs of the mineral mining industry. *MINING INDUSTRY*. 2018, No 6 (142), pp. 30-33. [In Russ].

8. Sokolov A.A. Methods of decision support in energy resource supply systems at machine-building enterprises. – Volgograd: Abstract of the dissertation, 2019. – 20 s.

9. Martynyuk M.V. Models and algorithms of intelligent control of parameters of regulating devices in digital power grids. – Nizhny Novgorod: Abstract of the dissertation, 2019. – 23 s.

10. Zaripova V.M., Kvasova V.O., Petrova I.Yu. Decentralized electricity market – new requirements for digitalization of business processes. – Engineering and Construction Bulletin of the Caspian Sea, 2020. – pp. 98-104.

11. Klyuev R.V., Gavrina O.A., Khetagurov V.N., Zasseev S.G., Ymirov B.Z. Forecasting the specific electricity consumption of the concentrating plant. Mining information and analytical bulletin (scientific and technical journal), 2020. – pp. 135-145.

12. Adel Naji, Badr Al Tarhuni, Jun-Ki Choi, Salahaldin Alshatshati, Seraj Ajena. Toward cost-effective residential energy reduction and community impacts: A data-based machine learning approach. – Energy and AI, Volume 4, June 2021, 100068.

Usmanova T. Kh., Isakov D. A. Important aspects of power costs of the mineral mining industry. *MINING INDUSTRY*. 2018, No 6 (142), pp. 30-33. [In Russ].

13. Shintaro Ikeda, Tatsuo Nagai. A novel optimization method combining metaheuristics and machine learning for daily optimal operations in building energy and storage systems. – Applied Energy, Volume 289, 1 May 2021, 116716.

14. Cheng Zhoua, Xiyang Chen. Predicting China's energy consumption: Combining machine

- learning with three-layer decomposition approach. – Energy Reports, Volume 7, November 2021. pp. 5086-5099.
15. Mining and processing of uranium ores. Monograph. Under the general editorship of A.P. Chernov. Kyiv. "Adef - Ukraine". 2001, - 238 p.
16. Electrification of mining production: Textbook for universities: In 2 volumes / Under the editorship of L.A. Puchkov and G.G. Pivnyak. - M.: Publishing House of Moscow State Mining University, 2007. - T. 2. - 595 p. (In Russ.).
17. Kaboli S., Selvaraj J., Rahim N. Longterm electric energy consumption forecasting via artificial cooperative search algorithm. Energy. 2016;115(1):857–871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.09.015>.
18. Meira de Oliveira E., Cyrino Oliveira F. L. Forecasting mid-long term electric energy consumption through bagging ARIMA and exponential smoothing methods. Energy. 2018;144(1):776–788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.12.049>.
19. Bornschlegl M., Bregulla M., Franke J. Methods-energy measurement – an approach for sustainable energy planning of manufacturing technologies. Journal of Cleaner Production. 2016;135(1):644–656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.059>.
20. Kupin, A., Shapovalov V., Lyashenko V., Sherstnov Y., Uchytel S. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF METHODS OF CALCULATION AND FORECASTING OF THE SPECIFIC ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION OF A MINING ENTERPRISE. Sciences of Europe, (147), p.p.106–115. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13382714.
21. A. Kupin, A. Uchitel V. Shapovalov, V. Lyashenko, S. Uchitel (2024). JUSTIFICATION OF REACTIVE POWER COMPENSATION TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF SUPPLY VOLTAGE OF SUBSTATIONS OF MINING AND PROCESSING PLANTS. Sciences of Europe, №149. Pp.51-60. DOI:5281/zenodo 13842719.
22. Sinchuk, O., Kupin, A., Sinchuk, I., Rohoza, M., & Plieshkov, P. (2020). Certain aspects concerning the development of a functioning scheme of the automated system to control energy flows of underground iron-ore enterprises. Mining of Mineral Deposits, 14(3), 101-111. <https://doi.org/10.33271/mining14.03.101>.
23. Sinchuk, O., Sinchuk, I., Beridze, T., Filipp, Y., Budnikov, K., Dozorenko, O., & Strzelecki, R. (2021). Assessment of the factors influencing on the formation of energy-oriented modes of electric power consumption by water-drainage installations of the mines. Mining of Mineral Deposits, 15(4), 25-33. <https://doi.org/10.33271/mining15.04.025>.
24. Biel K., Glock C. Systematic literature review of decision support models for energy-efficient production planning. Computers & Industrial Engineering. 2016;101:243–259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2016.08.027>
25. Wenqiang Jing, Junqi Yu, Wei Luo, Chujun Li, XinYi Liu. Energy-saving diagnosis model of central air-conditioning refrigeration system in large shopping mall. – Energy Reports, Volume 7, November 2021. – pp. 4035-4046.
26. Dominik Flick, Claudio Keck, Christoph Herrmann, Sebastian Thiede. Machine learning based analysis of factory energy load curves with focus on transition times for anomaly detection. – Procedia CIRP, Volume 93, 2020. pp. 461-466.
27. Thanh, L.X., & Bun, H.V. (2021). Identifying the efficiency decrease factor of motors working under power harmonic in 660V electric mining grids. Mining of Mineral Deposits, 15(4), 108-113. <https://doi.org/10.33271/mining15.04.108>.
28. Oleinik T.A., Lyashenko V.I., Chekushina T.V., Oleinik M.O. Justification of the efficiency and environmental safety of technologies and cyclone devices of a new generation for the beneficiation and processing of iron ore. *Ferrous metals*. -2021. - № 5, pp. 10-15. DOI: 10.17580/chm.2021.05.02.
29. Klyuev R. V., Bosikov I. I., Gavrina O. A., Lyashenko V. I. Assessment of operational reliability of power supply to developing ore mining areas at a high-altitude mine. Mining Science and Technology (Russia). 2021;6(3):211–220. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.17073/2500-0632-2021-3-211-220>.
30. Morgoeva A.D., Morgoev I.D., Klyuev R.V., Lyashenko V.I. Forecasting the load on the power grid as a way to effectively manage the consumption of electrical energy. News of Higher Educational Institutions of the Chernozem Region. 2021; 4(66);39-51.